

Local Government in Austria

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

Alexandra Schantl, Dalilah Pichler and Thomas Prorok

KDZ - Centre for Public Administration Research Austria

Partners

Eurac Research
Institute for Comparative Federalism
Italy

LMU Munich
Research Center for Public Procurement
Law and Administrative Cooperations
Germany

Autonomous University of Madrid
Institute of Local Law
Spain

Institut für Föderalismus
Institut du Fédéralisme
Institute of Federalism

University of Fribourg
Institute of Federalism
Switzerland

NALAS
Network of Associations of Local
Authorities of South East Europe
France

ximpulse
Ximpulse GmbH
Switzerland

KDZ
Center for Public Administration Research
Austria

Council of Europe
Congress of Local and Regional Authorities
France

Faculty of Political Science
and International Studies
University of Warsaw
University of Warsaw
Institute of Political Science
Poland

ZELS
Association of the Units of Local Self-Government
North Macedonia

University of the Western Cape
Dullah Omar Institute for Constitutional
Law, Governance and Human Rights
South Africa

Addis Ababa University
Center for Federalism and Governance Studies
Ethiopia

UNIVERSIDAD
NACIONAL DE
SAN MARTÍN

Universidad Nacional de General San Martín
School of Politics and Government
Argentina

SALGA
South African Local Government Association
South Africa

जवाहरलाल नेहरू विश्वविद्यालय
Jawaharlal Nehru University

Jawaharlal Nehru University
India

University of Technology Sydney
Institute for Public Policy and Governance
Centre for Local Government
Australia

National University of Singapore
Centre for Asian Legal Studies
Asia Pacific Centre for Environmental Law
Singapore

University of Western Ontario
Centre for Urban Policy and Local Governance
Canada

November 2021

The Country Report on Local Government in Austria is a product of the LoGov-project: “Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay”.

The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

LICENSE

CC BY 4.0

INFORMATION

Eurac Research
Viale Druso/Drususallee, 1
39100 Bolzano/Bozen – Italy

logov@eurac.edu
www.logov-rise.eu

SCIENTIFIC COORDINATION

Eurac Research: Karl Kössler

WP 1 – Local Responsibilities and Public Services

LMU Munich: Martin Burgi

WP 2 – Local Financial Arrangements

Universidad Autónoma de Madrid: Francisco Velasco Caballero

WP 3 – Structure of Local Government

University of Fribourg: Eva Maria Belser

WP 4 – Intergovernmental Relations of Local Government

NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South East Europe: Elton Stafa

WP 5 – People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making

Ximpulse GmbH: Erika Schläppi

EDITORIAL TEAM

KDZ – Centre for Public Administration Research
Austria: Alexandra Schantl, Dalilah Pichler, Thomas Prorok
Eurac Research: Karl Kössler, Theresia Morandell, Caterina Salvo, Annika Kress, Petra Malferttheiner

GRAPHIC DESIGN

Eurac Research: Alessandra Stefanut

COVER PHOTO

Marvin Van Hagen/Unsplash

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823961.

Contents

1. The System of Local Government in Austria	1
2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Austria: An Introduction	6
2.2. <i>Organization of Public Transport in Austria Focusing on Functional Urban Regions (City Regions)</i>	11
2.3. <i>Municipal Water and Wastewater Management in Austria</i>	16
2.4. <i>Social Housing: The Case of Vienna</i>	21
3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Austria: An Introduction	29
3.2. <i>Budget Transparency with Open Spending Austria</i>	33
3.3. <i>Effects of the Intragovernmental Transfer System on Financial Strength</i>	38
3.4. <i>The Role of EU Structural Funds for Austrian Local Governments and its Contribution to the Urban-Rural Interplay</i>	43
4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Austria: An Introduction	49
4.2. <i>Inter-Municipal Development Process ‘Lienzer Talboden’ Future Space</i>	55
4.3. <i>Administrative Association in Building Law: Region Vorderland</i>	60
4.4. <i>Post-Merger Evaluation: Future-Oriented Organizational Development in the City of Fehring/Styria</i>	63
5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Austria: An Introduction	67
5.2. <i>Management by Objectives in the Field of Compulsory Schooling</i>	70
5.3. <i>INKOBA: Inter-Communal Settlement Projects and Business Parks in Upper Austria</i>	75
5.4. <i>Austrian Conference of Spatial Planning: ÖROK</i>	80
6.1. People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making in Austria: An Introduction	86
6.2. <i>Open Government Initiative Vienna</i>	89
6.3. <i>People’s Participation in Vorarlberg: Bürgerräte and Gemeindeentwicklungsprojekte Götzis/Langenegg</i>	93
6.4. <i>Participatory Budget in the Vienna District of Margareten</i>	100

Local Financial Arrangements

3.4. The Role of EU Structural Funds for Austrian Local Governments and its Contribution to the Urban-Rural Interplay

Nikola Hochholdinger and Alexandra Schantl, *KDZ Centre for Public Administration Research Austria*

Relevance of the Practice

The Austrian financial equalization system provides financial resources to finance local governments tasks. Due to the specific framework conditions and challenges of urban local governments (ULGs) and rural local governments (RLGs), the question of how these funds can be distributed fairly between ULGs and RLGs seems to be a never-ending story. While RLGs want to have their structural challenges due to the rural exodus compensated by this intragovernmental transfer system, ULGs want to be reimbursed for their increased need for infrastructure development and their additional tasks due to the influx of people. However, there is a second level of redistribution in the form of an extensive subsidy system that leads to differentiated distribution effects with regard to urban and rural areas.

In this context EU funding has become more and more important over the last decades, in particular with regard to regional policy and development. For the EU-funding period 2014-2020 Austria has benefitted from the European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF) through four national programs with 4.92 billion supplemented⁶⁵ by EUR 5.74 billion of national co-financing.⁶⁶ The biggest part of the funding has been dedicated to the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) with 72.5 per cent, around 20 per cent to the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) and 8.2 per cent to European Social Fund (ESF). With less than one per cent of the planned funding, the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund (EMFF) is the smallest and least relevant program in Austria.

To implement both innovative inner-city and urban-regional initiatives in Austria the ESIF plays a decisive role. The scope of urban regional action according to integrated multi-level approaches in the administration (multi-level governance) in Austria would be considerably lower without start-up funding from the EU.

⁶⁵ European Commission, 'Country Data for Austria' (*European Structural and Investment Funds*, last updated 2021) <<https://cohesiondata.ec.europa.eu/countries/AT#>> accessed January 2021.

⁶⁶ Peter Mayerhofer, Julia Bachtrögler, Klaus Nowotny, and Gerhard Streicher, 'Quantitative Wirkungen der EU-Struktur- und Kohäsionspolitik in Österreich – ein Beitrag zu 25 Jahre Österreich in der EU' (WIFO 2020) 11.

However, the current funding structures and frameworks (complex intervention logic, multiple funding authorities/agencies, lack of coherence between the various EU funds and instruments) as well as the lack of long-lasting rollover funding or follow-up investments, hinder the sustainable use of EU funds both for the integrated development of urban regions and for bridging the urban-rural gap.

Description of the Practice

A recently published study⁶⁷ on quantitative effects of ESIF-funding in Austria has shown that EU funding in Austria clearly contributed to reduce spatial disparities in Austria over the last 25 years. According to the EU Rural-Urban-Typology the highest funding intensity – spending per capita – of the ESIF funds was found in peripheral rural areas (see figure below). This also indicates that RLGs ultimately benefited more from the funding than ULGs due to the different thematic and geographical orientation of the single ESIF programs.

Figure 6: Funding intensity of ESIF in Austrian districts 1995-2017⁶⁸

Since social, ecological and economic processes and challenges correspond less and less to administrative borders, also in Austria with the 2014-2020 funding period EU funds have been increasingly dedicated to functional areas as well as to the cooperation of ULGs with their - often rural - surrounding areas in order to strengthen territorial and social cohesion.

For urban-regional (urban-rural) measures it has been mostly resources from the European Structural and Investment Fund that come into effect; respectively from the ERDF and the

⁶⁷ Mayerhofer and others, 'Quantitative Wirkungen der EU-Struktur- und Kohäsionspolitik in Österreich', above.

⁶⁸ *ibid.*

EAFRD. Thus, the Austrian program ‘Investment in Growth and Jobs’ (Article 7 - Integrated and sustainable urban development) has supported, for instance, the Upper Austrian urban regions and urban-rural cooperation in Tyrol (CLLD)⁶⁹. The cooperation between the City of Villach and its surrounding regions works with LEADER⁷⁰ resources from the EAFRD. Other functional spaces that go beyond the Austrian national borders, such as the cooperation in the area of the Lienz Valley with Bruneck in South Tyrol, are supported by the EU’s Interreg programs.

However, EU funding shall not and cannot replace national funding. In order to be able to continue successful EU initiatives and projects even after EU funding has phased out, the ‘EU start-up funding’ needs to be secured in the long term through national (reform) programs. This applies above all to the integrated development of functional areas. A good example of how EU funds contribute to sustainable investment both in ULGs and RLGs is the Styrian Regional Development Law that came into force in 2018. The purpose of this law is to create the best prerequisites for a targeted cooperation between all governmental authorities (*Land*/region/local governments) concerned with economic and social development. A yearly amount of EUR 12 million is available for these tasks, distributed among the seven Styrian regions and spent on their own responsibility. The law incorporates citizens’ participation as an essential issue for the regions. The main superordinate goal is to equalize regional imbalances and to govern structural spatial development. The tasks are set on two levels:

- the regional government level (*Land* Styria): Development strategy framework for the entire province, coordination of regional strategies and spatial policies, tuning of flagship projects;
- the regional level: Coordination and enforcement of inter-municipal cooperation within the region, elaboration and realization of regional development strategies, proposals for appropriate projects, permanent monitoring.

The regional tasks are performed by so-called *Regionalverbände* (regional authority associations) and their authority independent bodies, the president, the board and the assembly. In the assembly the mayors and councilors of the participating municipalities are represented. There are currently seven *Regionalverbände*. Financial resources can be used for management tasks as well as for projects to benefit the regional populations (e.g. mobility improvement, logistic concepts, social procurement etc.). Since the available regional budget can also be used as co-financing for EU projects, there is additional funding for local projects and investments. Furthermore, the potential and willingness of both ULGs and RLGs to use EU funds for their local projects increases.

⁶⁹ Community Led Local Development Instrument.

⁷⁰ *Liaison entre actions de développement de l'économie rurale* – instrument of the EAFRD.

Assessment of the Practice

Although EU funding plays a minor role in Austria in relation to national funding, it has successively become more important in the last decades, especially in regional policy and development. Local governments have benefited from ESIF-funding through many different projects and conjoint initiatives and EU-funded projects have been crucial catalysts and promoters for starting innovative processes and implementing new and cooperative government structures especially on the regional level both in Austria and cross-border.

However, there are differences between ULGs and RLGs in absorbing EU-Funds. While RLGs benefit from the largest ESIF program in Austria – the EARDF – the funding opportunities for ULGs are limited for two reasons: the ERDF funds in Austria, where ULGs are potential beneficiaries, still focus on economic support for SMEs and research measures, while funds for sustainable urban development measures and investments are very limited. On the other side the majority of the EAFRD funds go to small RLGs, although ULGs with up to 30,000 inhabitants would be eligible.⁷¹

With the new approach on supporting functional areas since the last funding period 2014-2020 it seems that also ULGs will benefit better from EU-funding in future and that this territorial approach could not only strengthen cooperative regional governance but also cushion the urban-rural divide.

However, to successfully and sustainably use EU funding for functional areas improvements are still needed. This demand is also in line with both the current position paper of the Austrian Association of Cities and Towns⁷² for the funding period 2021-2027 and the findings of a recent Austrian Conference on Spatial Planning (ÖROK) study⁷³ that requests to strengthen the resource potentials of regions as actors for the attainment of programming objectives in order to improve the effectiveness of funding on local and regional level.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Legal Documents:

Styrian Regional Development Law (StLREG, *Steiermärkisches Landes- und Regionalentwicklungsgesetz*) and Amendment to the Styrian Regional Planning Law (*Änderung des Steiermärkischen Raumordnungsgesetzes*), XVII. GPStLT RV EZ 1912/1 AB EZ 1912/4

⁷¹ Ministry of Agriculture, Regions and Tourism, 'Austrian Programme for Rural Development 2014-2020' 73.

⁷² Austrian Association of Cities, 'Position paper (Summary): Cities & Urban regions 2020+ Positions of the Austrian cities and urban regions regarding the design of the EU grant decisions 2021-2027' (2019).

⁷³ Österreichische Raumordnungskonferenz ÖROK, 'Die regionale Handlungsebene stärken – Status, Impulse und Perspektiven' (publication series no 208, ÖROK 2020) 12.

Ministry of Agriculture, Regions and Tourism, 'Austrian Programme for Rural Development 2014-2020' <<https://www.bmlrt.gv.at/english/agriculture/rural-development/austrian-rural-development-programme-2014---2020---text-of-the-programme-after-its-first-amendment--version-2.1.html>>

Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications:

Austrian Association of Cities, 'Position paper (Summary): Cities & Urban regions 2020+ Positions of the Austrian cities and urban regions regarding the design of the EU grant decisions 2021-2027' (2019)

<https://www.staedtebund.gv.at/fileadmin/USERDATA/themenfelder/europa/2020__positionpaper_january2020.pdf>

European Commission, 'Country Data for Austria' (European Structural and Investment Funds, last updated 2021) <<https://cohesiondata.ec.europa.eu/countries/AT#>>

Mayerhofer P, Bachtrögler J, Nowotny K, and Streicher G, 'Quantitative Wirkungen der EU-Struktur- und Kohäsionspolitik in Österreich – ein Beitrag zu 25 Jahre Österreich in der EU (WIFO 2020)

Österreichische Raumordnungskonferenz ÖROK, 'Die regionale Handlungsebene stärken – Status, Impulse und Perspektiven' (publication series no 208, ÖROK 2020)

<https://www.oerok.gv.at/fileadmin/user_upload/O__ROK_SR_NR._208__2020__Reg_HE_online-Version.pdf>

Contacts

Local Government and the Changing
Urban-Rural Interplay
www.logov-rise.eu
logov@eurac.edu

This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020 re-
search and innovation programme under
grant agreement No 823961.

